

topAM BRIEFING

Developing ODS high temperature alloys tailored for AM

This topAM Briefing covers the latest project results including: modelling of the dispersoids, powder modifications, AM production of samples, and materials properties of the modified alloys.

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This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 958192.

WP1 Application and specification sheet

WP1 has already been completed and the deliverable of the specification sheets for the ferrules and the gas burner tip were submitted on time. These specification

sheets describe the materials' property goals, target environments and the component geometries. These deliverables lay the basis for the WP7 proof of principle.

WP2 Optimal computational design for LPBF based on ICME

Overall, a cross-disciplinary Integrated Computational Materials Engineering (ICME) approach has been employed to enable physics-based computational links between LPBF processing, microstructure evolution, mechanical and environmental properties.

The ICME approach was successfully used to rapidly screen combinations of three different alloy systems with multiple nanoparticle types and three different powder production strategies.

Computational design and refinement of nanoparticles and material compositions for different powder production strategies was performed on down-selected concepts based on performance

requirements, followed by optimization of LPBF process conditions to achieve optimal ODS alloy properties.

Throughout the tool's development, experimental data were used for model calibration, and key experiments designed to validate predictions. This not only accelerated both the tools and materials development, but also enabled the concurrent development of materials and processes.

Figure 1: Illustration of ODS alloy composition determination based on desired particle size distribution as dictated by property targets, and the identification of optimal LPBF process parameters based on creep stress modelling and build density.

WP3 LPBF component design

In WP3, an in-house OpenFOAM solver for the multiphysics optimization using the continuous adjoint approach was developed and validated using literature. The capabilities of the standard optimization solver of OpenFOAM are extended by including the heat transfer equation. A gas burner cooling head was

designed using the AI-enhanced OpenFOAM solver developed within topAM and a reduction of 32°C is expected to be achieved using the simulation (Figure 2). The burner was successfully manufactured via LPBF without using any internal support structures using the modified topAM alloys.

Figure 2: (a) Base gas burner geometry, (b) Results from the CHT simulation of temperature distribution at the front plate (top) and velocity distribution within the cooling head in base geometry, (c) Results from the CHT simulation of temperature distribution at the front plate (top) and velocity distribution within the cooling head (bottom) in the optimized cooling head design.

WP4 Powder production and modification

Throughout the topAM project, a multitude of powders have been produced and modified. Hundreds of kilograms of bulk material were supplied by the material producers for gas atomization at the research institutes. This resulted in extensive powder feedstocks for both the additive manufacturing process parameter optimization and the further modification of these powders to generate dispersion-strengthened components. Namely, a change in powder chemistry and morphology was achieved by

the processes of gas atomization reaction synthesis, mechanical alloying and decoration, extensive mixing, fluidized bed reactor, and freeze granulation and drying. Among these, the fluidized bed reactor stood out as the most promising process for the TiN-enriched NiCu alloy system (Figure 3 left), and the gas atomization reaction synthesis demonstrated best results for the TiN-containing Ni-based material (Figure 3 right).

Figure 3: Titanium nitrides on the nanoscale of NiCu- (left) and Ni-based (right) powder materials.

After determination of the most promising process routes and during the last phase of the project, respectively, final powder feedstocks were generated of the modified materials for component printing. In terms of the NiCu-based heat exchanger, this included the supply of TiN-enhanced Alloy 400 for the ferrules and temperature control devices. The Ni-based burner head instead was fabricated from TiN- and γ' -

strengthened alloys 699XA and 602CA, i.e. for the feed and oxygen tips, respectively.

To summarize, all tasks included in WP4 (powder production, powder modification, and powder characterization) could be accurately addressed within the project time.

WP5 LPBF and Post-Processing

In the topAM project, extensive additive manufacturing (AM) process development and detailed characterization were performed on samples produced using the Laser Powder Bed Fusion (LPBF) process. Powders manufactured through different modification routes were printed at two specialized manufacturing sites: Osnabrück University of Applied Sciences, focusing on the Ni-Cu-based alloy family, and RWTH-DAP (Digital Additive Production), concentrating on the Ni-based alloy family. Comprehensive analyses, including microstructural, mechanical, and corrosion performance evaluations, were conducted. Based on these results, the most promising alloys, demonstrating superior mechanical and corrosion performance, were selected for the fabrication of final components.

Key Outputs of Component Manufacturing

- **Ferrule and Temperature Control Device:** Produced using NiCu-based powder derived from post-internal nitridation modification via a fluidized bed reactor (alloy 400).
- **Burner Head:** Manufactured with TiN- and γ' -strengthened Ni-based alloys 699XA and 602CA, for the feed, and oxygen tips, respectively. The formation of nanosized TiN was confirmed in printed components, as shown in Figure 4 for alloy 699XA from in-situ internal nitridation modification route.

The fabrication of final components was successfully executed at the respective manufacturing sites, and the components were delivered to Linde for the final in-service testing and qualification as part of the proof-of-concept phase in the project.

Figure 4: Nanosized titanium nitrides observed in the printed nickel-based 699 alloy, with the input powder modified via in-situ internal nitridation during the atomization process.

WP6 Material properties

All long-term tests for various modified oxide-Long-term tests in various aggressive environments are nearing completion and are expected to conclude by the end of the year. Over these months, measurements have been conducted on different modified oxide-dispersion strengthened (ODS) materials, focusing on molten nitrate salts, steam oxidation, metal dusting and dry air oxidation.

As an example of completed analyses, results from steam oxidation tests are discussed. The graphs reveal steady state oxidation mechanism of the scale formation at both temperatures (750, 950 °C). After a 5,000-hour steam test at 750 °C, the exposed materials showed a very thin oxide scale as presented in Figure 5. The higher temperature (950 °C) showed accelerate degradation of the materials (Figure 6).

Figure 5: Cross sections of the exposed alloys in steam at 750 °C, A) AM 699XA, B) BULK 699XA, C) MAC-UN-699-G, D) MAC-ISIN-699

Figure 6: Cross sections of the exposed alloys in steam at 950 °C, A) AM 699XA, B) BULK 699XA, C) MAC-UN-699-G, D) MAC-ISIN-699

The performed analyses from the surface (not shown here) on the exposed specimens indicated a rich Cr oxide scale formation (Cr_2O_3). The cross sectioned microstructures in Figure 5 and 6 indicate good steam oxidation performance at 750 °C, thin Cr rich oxide scale formation, but at 950 °C (except MAC-UN-699-G) the exposed alloys underwent poor steam oxidation performance, the alloys developed internal oxidation (IOZ) region.

The deepest rate of IOZ was found at 950 °C for MAC-ISIN-699, AM 699XA and finally BULK 699XA. The IOZ was rich in only in Al_2O_3 . In MAC-ISIN-699 random crystals rich in TiO_2 was found on the surface also TiO_2 was found within the material but not in IOZ.

In both tests, the MAC-UN-699-G alloy demonstrated the lowest mass gain and good steam environment resistance, poor steam oxidation resistance was found in MAC-ISIN-699 mostly by the formation of TiO_2 phase and deep IOZ formation.

Figure 7: Mass gain of the material exposed for 5000 h in steam at A) 750 °C and B) 950 °C

WP7 Proof of principle

In October 2024, the burner test, which is the core part of WP7, has been performed at Linde Gas in Unterschleißheim.

Before the burner assembly, a computer tomography (CT) scan of the additive manufactured burner tips (oxygen tip from **SAC-ISIN-602** and feed tip from **MAC-ISIN-699**) has been performed to check for internal damages and compare the printed geometry with the designed geometry. Deviations of up to 1 mm could be observed in the connection section of the cooling coils.

The additive manufactured burner tips have been welded to an existing burner by the Linde Gas workshop. The burner was introduced to the side wall of the furnace and all gaps have been closed with ceramic fiber to prevent hot gases from exiting the furnace.

The test furnace is heated up to 1300 °C using a fully oxidizing burner. At this temperature the test burner was lit and slowly ramped up to full operating load at which the furnace reached a temperature of 1500 °C. CO concentrations at the outlet of the furnace have been measured and exceeded the measuring range of 5 vol.% of the gas analyzer, thus confirming the reducing atmosphere in the test furnace, which is responsible for the metal dusting damage of these types of burners.

After the test the burner tips have been cut from the burner for investigation post the burner test. An additional CT scan was performed to reveal any deformations occurred during the test. Further metallography investigation at the burner tip and at the weld seam is ongoing until the end of December 2024.

In parallel work progresses for the lifetime prediction model, life cycle assessment and prediction model for stable phases and oxide growth rate.

Figure 8: Picture of the test furnace at Linde Gas Unterschleißheim, where the burner was inserted from the side wall, so that during operation the front face of the burner could be observed from the other side (picture right side)

WP8 Dissemination, communication, exploitation

The topAM communication activities on LinkedIn, X (former Twitter) and our webpage continued.

We are also pleased that the project has already led to 15 publications. We invite you to view the latest at:

The influence of microstructural heterogeneities on high-temperature mechanical properties of additively manufactured γ' -forming Ni-based alloys. Venkatesh Pandian Narayana Samy, Frederike Brasche, Ivo Šulák, Bhupesh Verma, Benedikt Nowak, Zdeněk Chlup, Tomáš Záležák, Johannes Henrich Schleifenbaum, Ulrich Krupp, Christian Haase. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2024.104267>

Understanding the high-temperature deformation behavior of additively manufactured γ' -forming Ni-based alloys by microstructure heterogeneities-integrated creep modelling. Venkatesh Pandian Narayana Samy, Frederike Brasche, Fuyao Yan, Ivo Šulák, Betül Bezci, Benedikt Nowak, Ida Berglund, Ulrich Krupp, Christian Haase. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.addma.2024.104256>

Oxidation of additive manufactured 699XA Ni-based alloy under different atmosphere. Fernando Pedraza, Antoine Duval, Ivo Šulák, Benedikt Nowak, Thomas Kepa, Germain Boissonnet, Gilles Bonnet. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.corsci.2024.112333>

Establishing a process route for additive manufacturing of NiCu-based Alloy 400: an alignment of gas atomization, laser powder bed fusion, and design of experiments. Roth, JP., Šulák, I., Kruml, T. et al. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00170-024-14328-7>

The Dispersion-Strengthening Effect of TiN Nanoparticles Evoked by Ex Situ Nitridation of Gas-Atomized, NiCu-Based Alloy 400 in Fluidized Bed Reactor for Laser Powder Bed Fusion. Roth J-P, Šulák I, Gálíková M, Duval A, Boissonnet G, Pedraza F, Krupp U, Jahns K. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmmp8050223>

Steam Oxidation Resistance in a Long Term Exposure of the Modified Laser Powder Bed Fusion 699XA Alloy at High Temperature. T. Dudziak, E. Rząd, A. Polkowska, T. Polczyk, P. Rob, V. Narayana Samy, B. Verma, I. Šulák, B. Nowak, U. Krupp. <https://doi.org/10.31399/asm.cp.am-epri-2024p0171>

High-Temperature Steam Oxidation Behavior of VDM Alloy 699 XA Produced by Laser Powder Bed Fusion. Dudziak, T., Chandran, P., Nowak, B. et al. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11665-024-09882-w>

topAM General Assembly Meeting and topAM fall school, 28-30 October 2024, Gothenburg, Sweden

The topAM General Assembly meeting took place on 28.-29. October 2024, hosted by RISE Research Institutes of Sweden. In conjunction with the final topAM fall school took place on 28.-30. October 2024.

Since both meetings were held in parallel, the consortium and students joined for a lab tour at RISE and a real demo of the topAM post processing by company Euromaskin active in machinery and postprocessing (EM Vacuum Deburring - Euromaskin).

The partners had an in-dept discussion of all the technical points in all the WPs. All the WP leads presented the key results from the individual WPs and had fruitful discussions with all the partners in the consortium.

Figure 9: Group picture of the topAM consortium at the GA meeting

Figure 10: Group picture of the students who participated in the topAM fall school 2024

The topAM schools educate students about the fundamentals of topAM related topics, new methods developed in topAM, and recent results. RISE hosted the 2 day, topAM fall school 2024 intended to provide knowledge on new topAM findings and technologies for students at an early career stage. For the fall school this year a total of 22 students from all over Europe (70 % masters students and the rest early stage PhD researchers) took part in the school. The evening of the first day was reserved for a dinner event, where students interacted with each other in a casual environment. There was a special session in the second day dedicated for students to interact with all the scientists and researchers from the topAM consortium to further understand how additive manufacturing is being used as a method to design novel ODS alloys.

The students received an in-depth tour of RISE's excellent facilities along with detailed lectures on a broad range of topics within the field of AM. The knowledge gained will impact their research directly and influence their future careers!

MSE Congress 2024!

At the MSE Congress 2024 (Materials Science and Engineering) on 24-26 September 2024, Darmstadt, Germany, the topAM project organised a special symposium.

Under the topic "Functional Materials, Surfaces and Devices", the **Special Symposium F02: "High Performance Materials for Sustainable Energy Applications"** was organised by the coordinators of the funded projects under the LC-SPIRE-08-2020 call, e.g. Professor Ulrich Krupp, RWTH-IEHK, coordinator of topAM. This symposium addressed recent advances in the field of novel high performance materials and components (**according to aims of projects under the Horizon 2020 framework under, call LC-SPIRE-08-2020**) by addressing materials design concepts, new materials as bulk materials or as coatings (metallic and ceramic), and technologies for their development, with the final aim of manufacturing components for the industrial applications.

The sessions were planned for 2 days, with 25 lectures from various researchers from Europe and UK. All the presentation were well received in the audience and some further collaborations have been initiated. In addition, we also received new members joining the project outreach page on LinkedIn to gain further insights and updates regarding the project.

[Link to the Special Symposium.](#)